

Adrenal x Thyroid

Medimon (28)

3 Parafollicular C-Cell
3 Follicular C-Cell
1 Thyroid
3 CCH
3 Hashimoto
1 Graves
3 Adrenal Medulla
3 Adrenal Cortex
1 Adrenal
3 DBH Deficiency
3 Cushing
1 Addison

ATP (22)

Buildings (2)

1 Shield Electric
1 Thirsty's Haunted Mansion

Treatments (6)

1 Thyroid Removal
1 Levothyroxine
1 Methimazole
1 Droxidopa
1 Mifepristone
1 Hydrocortisone

Antibodies (2)

1 IgM
1 IgG

Adrenal x Pancreas

Medimon (28)

3 Alpha Cell
3 Beta Cell
1 Pancreas
3 Type 2 Diabetes
3 Type 1 Diabetes
1 Pancreatitis
3 Adrenal Medulla
3 Adrenal Cortex
1 Adrenal
3 DBH Deficiency
3 Cushing
1 Addison

ATP (22)

Buildings (2)

1 Digestum Aquarium
1 Thirsty's Haunted Mansion

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1 Insulin
1 Pancreatic Enzymes
1 Droxidopa
1 Mifepristone
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